

Special Forum: Teaching About the Palestinian - Israeli Conflict

Organized by Gamze Çavdar

Dr. Yael Berda is an Associate Professor in the Department of Sociology and Anthropology at Hebrew University and a fellow at Harvard School of Kennedy's Middle East Initiative. Her most recent book is Colonial Bureaucracy and Contemporary Citizenship (Cambridge University Press, 2022).

Dr. Sebnem Gumuscu is an Associate Professor of Political Science at Middlebury College. Her most recent book is Democracy or Authoritarianism: Islamist Governments in Turkey, Egypt and Tunisia (Cambridge University Press, 2023).

Dr. Hanan Hammad is a Professor of History, Director of Middle East Studies, and Department Chair of Women and Gender Studies at Texas Christian University. Her most recent book is Unknown Past: Layla Murad, the Jewish-Muslim Star of Egypt (Stanford University Press, 2022).

Dr. Wendy Pearlman is a Crown Professor of Middle East Studies and interim director of Middle East and North Africa Studies. Her most recent book, The Home I Worked to Make: Voices from the New Syrian Diaspora, will be published in July 2024 (Liveright).

Teaching a college class can be hyper-politicized everywhere in the world, but particularly in the United States. College classrooms have become a battleground for many polarizing views: Critical race theory, LGBTQTI+, DEI (diversity, equity, and inclusion), migration, vaccine mandates, and genocide are to name a few. All sides often feel isolated, discriminated against, misunderstood, and

complain that unfair advantage is given to those who are on the other side (Jentleson et al. 2023, Pace 2021). The Palestinian-Israeli conflict is no different. As soon as such words as Hamas, apartheid, terrorism, occupation, etc., enter the classroom, the temperature goes sky-high, especially since October 7th, 2023, the beginning of the war in Gaza.

This piece aims to share the experiences and pedagogical approaches of four scholars who regularly teach about the Palestinian-Israeli conflict in their classes. We share these experiences with the readers of MENA Politics hoping that they encourage us to actively reflect our own experiences in the classroom, improve our teaching practices, and enhance student learning.

The four scholars who were individually interviewed are diverse on many grounds. First, they teach in different disciplines, namely political science, history, and sociology. Second, they teach in institutions located in different parts of the world. Third, as the rest of the article demonstrates, the scholars use many different strategies and sources tailored to the needs of their students. Lastly, they teach in different languages and use a multitude of original sources.

Despite these differences, the scholars interviewed also share many commonalities. One major characteristic they have in common is they all have extensive experience in the MENA region either because they originally come from a MENA country or spent considerable time in the region, living, studying, teaching, and conducting research. The scholars interviewed are—in alphabetical order—Dr. Yael Berda, Associate Professor in the Department of Sociology and Anthropology at Hebrew University (Israel) and a fellow at Harvard School of Kennedy's Middle East Initiative, Dr. Sebnem Gumuscu, Associate Professor in the Department of Political Science at Middlebury College (USA), Dr. Hanan Hammad, Professor of History and Director of Middle East Studies and the Department Chair of Women and Gender Studies at Texas Christian University (USA), and Dr. Wendy Pearlman, Professor of Political Science and the interim director of the Mid-

dle East and North Africa Studies Program at Northwestern University (USA). Three of the interviews took place on Zoom, lasting about an hour each, while we received written answers for the fourth interview.

At the expense of stating the obvious, two disclaimers must be stated here: First, it is necessary to highlight at the outset that there is no single way to teach about this or any other conflict nor our scholars claim that theirs is the best way. These scholars are invited for an interview because they do what educational institutions are supposed to do, that is to teach. In the current highly polarized political environment, this is an extremely courageous thing to do.

The second obvious disclaimer is that this article will not magically solve all the challenges that we face in relation to teaching about the Palestinian-Israeli conflict. These classes will remain contested as long as the conflict itself remains hyper politicized, deeply polarized, and unresolved, because teaching a topic in a classroom eventually mirrors the topic in the real world. Having said that we hope the readers of MENA Politics find these conversations as inspiring as we did and benefit from them to improve their own classroom experiences.

Each section in this article highlights commonalities as well as differences as outlined by our four colleagues. In the Appendix, our readers can find a list of sources that the interviewees use in their classes and have kindly shared with us.

1. KNOWING YOUR STUDENTS AND INTRODUCING YOURSELF

Instructors must know their students because the information about the community of students will deeply shape how the course is designed, lectures are prepared, and the discussions are organized, among others. As instructors, we design our courses with certain objectives in mind and then think about the strategies that help us meet these objectives. Therefore, the following factors will have to be considered in the course design: The location of the institution, the characteristics (or composition) of the student body, such as language skills, the depth of knowledge about the region and the conflict(s) in question as well as their personal attachments and emotional investments (Soria & Stubblefield, 2015). Understanding the latter will also enable instructors to identify the triggers during the conversations and take preemptive measures to contain tension. As a result, it is impossible to teach the same course to a group of students with similar backgrounds and political leanings versus another group consisting of extremely diverse views, variable depth of knowledge, and backgrounds.

This is not a one-time, linear process during which one departs from an initial point and arrives at the destination or discovers the magical formula to be repeated each year. It is, rather, a messy and iterative process that includes an instructor's self-assessments and reassessments, design and redesign, success, and failure—sometimes, all at the same time. What works one year does not guarantee that it will work the next, especially in a time of rapid political change, like the one we are currently experiencing. Undoubtedly, the ongoing political developments in the region will require instructors to constantly engage in this iterative process of assessing and reas-

sessing their courses to make sure the objectives are met.

An instructor's own positionality also potentially shapes the way a topic is taught and covered in the classroom. The term "positionality" assumes that the social and political context shapes our identity, which in turn affects our emotional attachments, values, and biases. As Klesse (2010) points out "The perspective of positionality strives for an understanding of the manifold and varying impacts of the interconnected oppressive forces around 'race'/ethnicity, class, gender, sexuality, age, and disability on the life experiences of individuals" (11). The instructor's reflections on their own positionality might enable students to engage in a critical reflective discussion, create space for an open conversation and be active participants in their own learning experience.

Dr. Berda teaches *Society in Israel, Sociology of Law and the Bureaucracy in the State* in Hebrew University to an extremely diverse body of students that includes "mainstream Israelis, Palestinian citizens of Israel, Jewish settlers from the West Bank and Palestinian residents of East Jerusalem." In response to the question as to how her identity and positionality might have influenced the way she approaches to this topic, Dr. Berda said:

In terms of my background, my father is French-Tunisian and my mother grew up in the United States. My family faced a lot of economic hardship and marginalization, in ways that they weren't always even conscious of. My father never really thought his Tunisian origins mattered in Israel, but they did. Realizing that really shifted my worldview and life trajectory. I discuss the importance of recognizing privilege, what it means to be a first-generation university student, and how being an "outsider" and

not part of the traditional Israeli elite affects one's perspective. I don't necessarily share all the personal details, but I think the examples I use and the ways I frame things make it clear that I'm speaking from a particular set of experiences. I find that helps students connect the material to real lives. I openly tell them about my previous career as a human rights and public interest lawyer and activist, before turning to academia. My belief that knowledge should be in service of social change infuses my teaching. I'm clear that I have political opinions that are on the left, and that my stances are public, such as on my Twitter. I prefer to be upfront so students don't have to guess where I'm coming from. I think my students appreciate the transparency, and it pushes them to be more reflective about their own positionalities. But it certainly means I likely get fewer right-wing students, as they know what to expect from me. I'm sure my identity and politics influence which texts I assign and how I frame them, but I do think it's important to include a range of scholarly perspectives, not just my own. My goal is to give them tools to critically examine the narratives they've grown up with and to wrestle with the contemporary situation and their own place in it. Being open about my background and commitments is central to my pedagogical approach. Hopefully it facilitates deeper reflection for all of us, even if some students inevitably disagree with my stances. Critiquing structures of power and connecting scholarship to lived experiences is core to my understanding of what sociology should be, both within and beyond the classroom.

Dr. Gumuscu teaches *Contemporary Conflicts in the Middle East, Politics of the Middle East and North Africa*, and *International Politics of the Middle East* to a group of students that she characterizes as "quite progressive". Dr. Gumuscu feels that her positionality as an instructor from Turkey, not

near the territories in conflict, and yet still from the region, has been advantageous. She states:

I'm from Turkey and do not have a personal connection to the conflict, arguably giving me a position of neutrality. Most students also appreciate that I'm from the region and am not an outsider teaching about the MENA.

Bringing in the discussion on positionality can be tricky though and it is not found effective by all instructors. In introducing herself to the class, Dr. Pearlman focuses on communicating to students the scholarly experience that she brings to the topic:

I tell them that I have lived in the West Bank, I have lived in Gaza, and I have lived in Israel. I studied Palestinian politics and I've studied Israeli politics and I've written books on these topics. I studied at a Palestinian university in the West Bank and at an Israeli university in Jerusalem. On the first day of class, more than emphasizing my own personal attachments, I try to establish my credibility. Of course, I have opinions and political commitments. We're on planet Earth. We watch the news, we watch politics, and we all have personal attachments and relationships that shape our stances. We're not robots! But here in this classroom, my job and my obligation is to be as fair and as scholarly as possible in providing readings that I think are credible, valuable, and present a range of perspectives. I want to provide knowledge and analyses so that students have the tools that they need to understand and to make their own judgments.

Dr. Pearlman teaches in a private university in a suburb of Chicago. In her 15-person seminar on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict body, about a third of the students are Jewish, occasionally one or two students are Arab

or Muslim, and many are political science majors with very little background who are taking the seminar to satisfy a requirement. In this course, as well as in her lecture course on Middle East politics where she devotes three sessions to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, she finds that many students almost feel embarrassed by their lack of knowledge. She explains that they say things like, “I know this issue is really important and a lot of people have opinions, but I don’t know enough to have opinions. I wish I did but I don’t even know where to begin.”

Dr. Hammad has been teaching two courses at Texas Christian University that partially cover the conflict, namely *Modern Middle East* and *Women in the Middle East*. Dr. Hammad, originally from Egypt, describes her institution and the study body in the following way:

The name of the institution speaks a lot about the nature of the university: It is Texas and it’s Christian.... The institution is historically and now predominantly a white institution. Our students are not only white but also conservative. The tuition is very high, so it also targets mostly economically comfortable students. Some students are probably not quite at ease with the material I teach, not only relevant to the conflict, but to other things, like, for example, the American role in Iraq, the American invasion of Iraq, the American policy in general in the Middle East. Some of them actually have a hard time processing it.

In Dr. Hammad’s experience, talking about her positionality opens the door for a conversation with some students who feel quite isolated. In a recent example, a male, Jewish student from California and his mother, who are of Moroccan Jewish origins, grew up spending summers in Israel and his best

friend is of Egyptian Jewish origin. “There is no one around him to share his identity, and actually, he felt we relate.” Every once in a while, Dr. Hammad receives emails from former students about her critical perspective saying, “how difficult it was for them when they encountered this perspective, but how much they appreciate now and understand it.”

At other times, however, Dr. Hammad’s Egyptian identity is also put into questions by her students:

So, student evaluations sometimes actually say, “If she is upset about American policy in the Middle East, why doesn’t she go back to the Middle East?” And I think, I wish to tell them, “If you’re happy with the American policy in the Middle East, why don’t you go live in the Middle East?”

2. ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

Most of our interviewees do not teach a class exclusively on the Palestinian-Israeli conflict. Rather, they cover the conflict through broadly Middle Eastern themed classes. One aspect that the scholars emphasize is that they use the same conceptual frameworks, terms, and theories throughout their classes and do not designate special lenses for this topic. Depending on the discipline and the specific foci of the course, these concepts and theories do differ, obviously. However, it is still possible to use the most-commonly used analytical frameworks as European imperialism and colonialism, and nationalism.

As a historian, Dr. Hammad explains how she designs her courses around certain concepts that she considers key in understanding the conflict:

In the modern Middle East class, I start by exploring where the problem originated. By this point, we have already covered European imperialism in the Middle East, the Arab Renaissance (Nahda), and state adjustments for self-defense, which James Galven refers to as “developmentalism” in the textbook. This background allows students to easily grasp the context of Europe, the Middle East, and Palestine. In my courses I emphasize that the issues in the Middle East were not unique to the region; they were part of a broader transformation. This includes European imperialism and the contribution of Jews in the region to the Renaissance. It becomes clear to the students that the origin of the conflict was largely imposed from outside, particularly by Europe, rather than being inherent to the Middle East or Palestine. We discuss how developments in Palestine before the accelerations that led to the establishment of Israel following WWII paralleled those in Egypt, Iraq, and Syria, focusing on the Renaissance, adjustments, and European imperialism.

Dr. Pearlman states that while acknowledging the sensitivities and identities that some of her students might have surrounding this topic and asking her students to be respectful of these sensitivities, she adopts the same approach in all her political science classes regardless of the subject and does not treat this conflict differently. Dr. Pearlman states:

I try to teach it just like I would teach any political science class, which is by focusing on the principles we bring to social science. What is evidence? How do we assess evidence? What are theories? How do we apply theories to make sense of the social and the political world? That has been my approach, to try to be as academic and as analytical and as rigorous as possible, and not put this topic in its own special category.

3. ADOPTING A HISTORICAL APPROACH

The interviewees agree that it is impossible to teach about this conflict including the current events without paying attention to history and covering considerable historical facts. Therefore, the consensus is to provide a historical context starting from as early as the end of the 19th century, early 20th century and the British mandate (1918-1948). All interviewees also discuss the current events while contextualizing them within history.

Dr. Pearlman states that her historical approach also applies to the talks she gives:

I take a tremendously historical approach when teaching about the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. This is true not only in my classes but in every talk I give on the subject. For example, I’ve given several talks related to Israel and Palestine since October 7th, and I start every single one in the 19th century. I don’t know how to approach this topic unless I start with Ottoman Palestine and the beginnings of the Zionist movement in Europe.

Although all four scholars adopt a historical approach, what aspects of history will be covered, how history will be interpreted and how students will perceive the history will significantly vary. Dr. Berda’s extremely diverse community of students is a testament to these multiple realities. Dr. Berda explains:

Since the escalation in October, there are two different timelines people are operating on. For Israelis, everything revolves around what happened on October 7th - the hostage crisis, the quarter million people who had to evacuate their homes in the north and south, and the sense of trauma. Meanwhile, in Gaza and to some extent the West Bank and East Jerusalem, their time-

line revolves around the events since the beginning of the war and the tens of thousands of deaths since then amidst the starvation and devastation there. Navigating what is possible and impossible to discuss on campus right now is extremely volatile.

4. MOVIES-DOCUMENTRIES-NOVELS

The scholars we interviewed report using strategies of critical pedagogy and utilizing movies, documentaries and even novels as supplemental course material. Sources of critical pedagogy offer many advantages to instructors. First, they break the routine and capture student attention to an issue/scenario. As digital natives, the new generation of students greatly appreciate course material other than text. The downside is this type of material could direct students' attention to other topics away from the course content. Therefore, it is best to be paired with a list of questions for students to consider.

Second, visual sources, including maps, pictures, cartoons, movies, and documentaries help many students who have never been to the region begin comprehending the subject matter and its complexities. Instructors have many options to choose from based on the course objectives. A suggested list is recommended by some interviewees in the Appendix.

5. PREPARING THE CLASS FOR EXPECTED DISAGREEMENTS AND SETTING UP THE PARAMETERS OF DISCUSSIONS

While disagreements are normal, expected and welcomed in a classroom where political and social topics are discussed, as instructors, it is our responsibility to make sure that all students feel they are included in the discus-

sions, their views and identities are respected, and the classroom discussions are productive. In the current environment where the *neutral middle ground* seems to be shrinking, the polarization is accelerating, every word we use is being scrutinized, and the freedom of speech is coming under threat, this is not an easy task.

All four scholars interviewed for this article recognize the growing tensions in the classroom. As such, they adopt carefully selected strategies to preempt and contain tension that would undermine student learning. It is also important to remember that many campuses in the U.S. have staff on campus especially designated to train students and faculty to have conversations about sensitive topics. They can be invited to the classroom before the topic is introduced. It's not clear (probably unlikely) if some academic institutions in the MENA region have a similar set up.

Some institutions seem to have prepared their campuses to hold conversations about sensitive topics better than others. Middlebury's *Engaged Listening* project is one of them. Dr. Gumuscu explains how the project was helpful in containing the tension although it was not successful in completely prevent it. She states:

I have been trying to follow the dialogic classroom model since 2021 when I joined Middlebury's Engaged Listening project, which aimed to improve faculty's facilitation skills for difficult conversations in their classrooms. Since I have been teaching politics of the MENA, I took part in this initiative to improve my facilitation skills. The dialogic classroom model I follow includes community agreements for respectful exchange of views, agreements to disagree with civility, listening exercises, practicing different question styles (questions of curi-

osity), and structured dialogue once or twice during the semester. This dialogic design complements the academic material I teach on the region, including the nature and the history of the Israel-Palestine conflict, and asks students to share their personal stories, personal connections to Israel and Palestine, and their fears and hopes. I tailor our dialogue questions to the region's conjecture as well as our campus climate. For example, in the Spring of 2021, I built a dialogic classroom around the Politics of the MENA and facilitated two dialogues after teaching my students dialogic practices. I intended to have only one dialogue on Israel-Palestine at the end of the semester (the dialogue question was: Share a personal experience that shaped your perspective on the conflict). As we approached the end of the semester, another war erupted in Gaza in May 2021; amidst this new cycle of conflict, our campus was thrown into a deep controversy. Different student groups clashed with each other. To respond to this campus controversy, I decided to facilitate a second dialogue about how we talk about Israel/Palestine on our campus. While the first dialogue was about the region and students' connections to Israel or Palestine, the second dialogue took the issue much closer to home and centered on our own challenges intertwined with the conflict in the region (the dialogue question was: When have you felt pulled in different directions on our campus controversy?). Students' reactions during the debrief and self-reflection were quite positive. They appreciated the safety of the dialogue setting and having the opportunity to hear others' views and stories in a dialogue facilitated by a professor.

All scholars also state that they find it helpful at the outset to outline the parameters of what is and what is not allowed in the classroom. Dr. Berda, for instance, emphasizes that the classroom needs to be a safe place to

have a conversation and that her students are exposed to multiple perspectives. Dr. Pearlman sets up the parameters by telling everyone to be respectful of sensitivities:

And I try to acknowledge, usually on the first day of class - the first day of the seminar or the first session within the lecture class - that this is a topic that brings up a lot of passions and a lot of emotions. It often taps into identities that students hold dear. It's a topic to which many students in the class have deep personal attachments. I want to be respectful of those and I hope everyone will be respectful of those. And we're also hear to learn, to analyze, and to understand.

Dr. Hammad sets up the parameters of the discussions at the very beginning by welcoming all questions and comments and clarifying what will not be tolerated:

When I introduce the theme of the Arab-Israeli conflict in my classes, I always encourage students to ask any questions, share perspectives, or make comments. Particularly, I emphasize that I would feel like a loser if they hesitated to share a question or a comment with me or the class. I make it clear that everything is welcome - questions, comments, critiques, perspectives, whatever. However, I strictly do not allow any form of anti-Semitism, Arabophobia, Islamophobia, etc. It's important to remind students that this conflict cannot be a vehicle for any form of racism. This approach helps students reflect and process their language, and it creates a space for open discussion and critical thinking, which is essential for understanding complex issues like this.

When tension starts building up, one possible strategy is to bring the attention back to the text. Dr. Pearlman continues:

In my experience, it's actually a lot less common for tensions to arise in the classroom than people expect. When they arise, they rarely relate to course materials. Instead, the greatest sources of tension are things that people are bringing from outside class — current events, identity concerns, personal attachments, or emotions. Rarely do I find that students do a reading and say, "Oh, this reading made me so upset." So if there are tensions, an instructor can try to bring the class back to the academic core, which is readings and our discussion of the readings. And if the discussion starts to go in a direction that you, as the instructor, don't think is productive, you can always reign it back in and say 'Let's turn to p. 145. What is the author arguing here ...'"

On her first day of class in the seminar, Dr. Pearlman has students read a short article from a news source that talks about how this conflict generates intense emotions and passions. Then the class discusses what emotions and passions the conflict creates. This allows students to address the reality of the feelings Israel and Palestine elicit, but also invites them to take a social science approach to scrutinizing those feelings as a kind of puzzle to explain. Dr. Pearlman finds this approach useful:

You recognize that tension is a part of this discussion, but then immediately put on your social scientific, analytical hat. We have a discussion - why is it so? Why does it create so much passion? Some people say, well, because religion is involved, or because of the long history of the conflict, or because so many actors are involved, or because of the sheer cumulative effect of violence. We have that discussion on the first day, and I find that students often refer back to it throughout the course.

Undoubtedly, the events unfolding since October 7th and the casualties on both sides will significantly increase the tension in the classroom posing further challenges to all instructors. Dr. Berda explains the general feelings in Israel and the difficulty of teaching to her extremely diverse students:

Because one of the things that I think people don't know so much about is that on the seventh of October, it wasn't just the attack of Hamas. It was also the total failure of the Israeli state and the summation of public services. Despite knowing that you can't hold 5 million people without rights, despite everything that I know from my research and from activism. At the end of the day there was always a sense that if something happens, the worst could be avoided, and that people would come to save people. And, just you had this thing where for hours and hours and hours people were left alone. Complete abandonment without security forces coming to help them without. People were calling on the phone or sending messages: "Where is the state? Where is the military?" And I think the sense of abandonment is one of the most traumatic things for Israelis, but of course it's turned most Israelis completely callous to Palestinian suffering.

Dr. Berda adds that she is “approaching it all more slowly and carefully now—not politically careful, but treating it all as a traumatic situation in a sense. I give more time for students to process things with each other.” Dr. Berda continues:

My approach in the past was very critical. I would tell my students that I know how explosive the material is, but that we're opening things up, opening wounds, and we're going to be able to talk about it - not just the Israeli-Palestinian issue, but also issues like the internal colonialism of Jews from

Arab countries and Africa within Israel. But I don't think I'm going to do that in quite the same way going forward. One thing I'm going to do more of is allowing students to figure things out more for themselves through questions about the origins of the situation and how debates have shifted over time. I also intend to give more time for students to discuss in groups and learn from each other's experiences and interpretations of the readings.

Conclusion

This article has shared the pedagogical strategies and experiences of five scholars who regularly teach the Palestinian-Israeli conflict in their classes. As the war continues, and the tension continues to rise in the region, we know there is no shortcut to overcome the difficulties in the classroom and create perfect settings conducive to learning. We also know that such a classroom could only be present once a peaceful and just solution agreed by both sides is found to this conflict. Until then, it is our hope that our readers find these strategies inspiring for their courses. ♦

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References

Jentleson, Bruce, Eric Mlyn, Candis Watts Smith, Kathryn Whetten, and Gary Bennett. 2023. "Inclusive Leadership Roundtable: Navigating Sensitive Topics in Your Teaching and Research Spaces," available at <https://www.facultyadvancementnetwork.org/navigating-sensitive-topics> (accessed March 14, 2024).

Klesse, Christian. 2010. "Teaching on 'race' and ethnicity: problems and potentialities related to 'positionality' in reflexive and experiential approaches to teaching and learning" *Enhancing Learning in the Social Sciences*, 2:3, 1-27, DOI: 10.11120/elss.2010.02030003

Pace, Judith L. 2021. *Hard Questions: Learning to Teach Controversial Issues*. Rowman & Littlefield Publishers.

Soria, K. M., & Stubblefield, R. (2015). Knowing Me, Knowing You: Building Strengths Awareness, Belonging, and Persistence in Higher Education. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 17(3), 351-372. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1521025115575914>

APPENDIX: Sources Recommended by Interviewees:

Background

Aly, Abdel Monem Said, Shai Feldman, and Khalil Shikaki, *Arabs and Israelis: Conflict and Peacemaking in the Middle East*, 2nd Edition (London and New York: Bloomsbury, 2022).

Bashkin, Orit, December 11, 2023, "The Before: History in Times of Khara" *Critical Inquiry*, available at <https://rb.gy/n8slt9>

Beinin, Joel and Lisa Hajjar. 2014. *Palestine, Israel, and the Arab-Israeli Conflict: A Primer*, MERIP, available at http://merip.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/Primer_on_Palestine-IsraelMERIP_February2014final.pdf

Gelvin, James. 2011. *The Modern Middle East: A History* (New York: Oxford University Press).

Lustick, Ian S. 1990. "Changing Rationales for Political Violence in the Arab-Israeli Conflict" *Journal of Palestine Studies*, Vol. 20, No. 1: pp. 54-79.

Lustick, Ian S. 2019. *Paradigm Lost: From Two State Solution to One-State Reality* (University of Pennsylvania Press).

Shlaim, Avi. 2023. *Three Worlds: Memoirs of an Arab Jew* (Oneworld Publications)

Weiss, Philip. 2015. "An exhibit of iconic 1948 photos" *Mondoweiss*, available at <http://mondoweiss.net/2015/01/exhibit-photos-journey>

Documentaries/Movies

5 Broken Cameras (2011)

Disturbing the Peace (2016)

The Holy Land: A Year in the West Bank (2014)

Netanyahu, America and the Road to War in Gaza (2023)

The Present (2020)

Novels

Tolan, Sandy. 2006. *The Lemon Tree: An Arab, a Jew, and the Heart of the Middle East* (New York: Bloomsbury)

Shibli, Adania and Elisabeth Jaquette. 2020. *Minor Detail* (New Directions).

Youtube

Leila Khaled Interview: *Palestine is an International Liberation Struggle*, available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6BB-vzyKL-G4>

Suad Amiry, "My Work, My Hobby," *Tedx-Ramallah*, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bk7joCi-gXs>

First Woman to Hijack a Plane: Leila Khaled, available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Eky-WoXE2eVQ>

CNN: Activist, Rachel Corrie, killed by bulldozer in Israel, available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3aFc-joTxooo>

The Pain Doesn't Go Away - Rachel Corrie's Parents on Reality Asserts Itself (Part 1), available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=95vzQGGxmF8>

The Pain Doesn't Go Away - Rachel Corrie's Parents on Reality Asserts Itself (Part 2), available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hMX-QvRXN8Kw>

The Pain Doesn't Go Away - Rachel Corrie's Parents on Reality Asserts Itself (Part 3), available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E9oK0HvABPs>

Palestine Pre-1947, available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vjEBQ_bE7uA

The History of Palestine, available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n3bxj1u-vDXU>

Israeli Soldier Reveals 1948 Palestinian Genocide and Zionist Ideology of Ethnic Cleansing, available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p8I-jnRsRPCQ>

Contemporary Issues

Ethan Bronner, “The Bullets in My In-Box,” *New York Times*, January 25, 2009, http://www.nytimes.com/2009/01/25/weekinreview/25bronner.html?_r=2&ref=weekinreview

Various pieces from *Foreign Affairs* and *Journal of Democracy*, various podcasts like *Ezra Klein*, *Today Explained*, and *Democracy Paradox*